

Estimation of Liver Disorder and its Correlation Factors in Modern World using Data Mining Techniques

Dr. Aneeshkumar A. S.^{*1}, Dr. S. Ramachandran², Dr. SripriyaArunachalam³, Dr. Monika Gupta⁴

¹Head, Department of Information System Management,
Alpha Arts and Science College, Porur, Chennai

²Chief Development Officer, Suryadatta Group of Institutes, Pune, India

³Vice Principal, HOD Department of Computer Science,
Alpha Arts and Science College, Porur, Chennai, India

⁴Associate Professor, Chandigarh Business School of Administration,
Chandigarh Group of Colleges, Landran (Mohali), Punjab, India

aneeshkumar.alpha@gmail.com¹, ram.89035@gmail.com², priyaarun02@gmail.com³,
monika18gupta@gmail.com⁴

Abstract

Knowledge recognition is an important task for any research work and which need either qualitative or quantitative dataset to attain the knowledge patterns. Various independent and hybrid applications of Machine learning Algorithms, Statistics and Relational data base management queries are used as part of Data mining in industry for the information retrieval. Liver is a primary reactor for any substances in the body and the biological changes with respect to liver is always closely linked to the lifestyle, stress and psychological factors. The study of physiological and psychological changes in association with liver dysfunction will lighten for future researches. This research aims to find the conjunctions of most influenced symptoms in alcoholic fatty liver disorder by applying support and confidence to the Reverse Sequential Covering Algorithm.

Keywords: Data mining; Reverse Sequential Covering Algorithm; Support; Confidence; Correlation; Regression.

1. Introduction

Liver disorder may grow from any simple inflammation to liver cirrhosis. In India the cause of liver dysfunction can be classified as three categories which are infection due to hepatitis virus and fatty liver owing to excessive consumption of alcohol or calories. Hepatitis virus can be classified as A, B, C, D and E, but D and E are sexually transmitted and it can see very rarely in India. Hepatitis A and B are less sensitive, easily curable and infected through non-highgenic food and water substances [1]. The treatment cost for the remaining hepatitis is relatively high and the effect is less in some peoples and so some of them will not complete the course of treatment [2]. According to Globocan estimates in 2008, the death rate due to liver related disease in worldwide is 478,300 males and 217,600 females and the estimated newly infected cases in each year is 522,400 male and 225,900 female respectively [3]. In death population 15.76 percentage of male and 18.34 percentage of females are from the developed countries, but the remaining large number (above 80 percentage of death and infection for both gender) are from developing countries like India [4]. The estimates identified that around 26,000 liver cirrhosis patients are died in each year and it is considered as twelfth leading death cause in worldwide [5].

Data mining is a process which includes many techniques to extract the exact knowledge from a large scale of multidimensional data. The methods which are used in data mining are well known and most applied in many research fields as well as government and corporate sectors for their knowledge discovery. The data mining techniques are become famous, because of the accuracy and visualization of information in any predictive or descriptive analysis [6]. Data mining uses

algorithmic models and statistical methods to expose clandestine patterns from large volume of data [7]. Discovering patterns is an important task and these patterns are useful for decision making in medical, business and scientific domains. Medical institutions are enriched with multidisciplinary data about patients' past history and present situation, but the major challenges faced by them is pattern analysis, where traits of an individual will not be studied for disease prediction or further treatment [8, 9].

Medical domains are enriching with significant and non-significant factors which are collected from various clinical and physical observations. These observed values are the part of diagnosis, some of them are directly influenced the disease and others are considered as indirectly influenced symptoms. But numerous attributes does not have role in diagnosis and so the identification and selection of necessary is an unavoidable process to achieve better predictions.

In influencing factor selection, ranking is adopted from information theory [10] to determine the importance of an individual data from the total. Feature selection algorithms are normally used to identify the influencing factors and these are classified into four broad categories namely wrappers, filters, hybrid and meta-heuristic methods [11]. Wrappers use algorithms to estimate the worth of the factors. In this predictive model, the new subsets are used to build a model and that is tested on a hold-out set to count error rates for scoring the subset. So it results the best fit features for the model and the predictive accuracy is used to decide the goodness of the subset selection. Wrappers are computationally expensive for dataset with large number of factors [12].

2. Liver Disorder

The liver disorder is considered as the dysfunction of liver due to any damage and that is visible with the variation of liver enzymes in blood streams. Liver is associated with almost every organ in human body and it has a vital role for the survival. Initially, liver diseases are diagnosed from the results of liver function test. Though this, the liver disease cannot be predicted at earlier stage. The variations in liver enzymes from normal to abnormal range are the basics of liver disorder and this variation differs according to the depth and intensity of the dysfunction. But the type of liver disorder can be identified with other clinical factors and computerized images.

Initially, the symptoms and consequences of liver disorder are unknown or less effective, and so it does not deserve much more consciousness [13]. The liver disorder is an outcome of directly or indirectly controlling factors. The direct factors are considered as a variety of viruses, alcohol consumption and obesity. The indirect factors are the after effects of other diseases and genetics. These conditions may cause liver failure that occurs gradually over many years and where the large parts of the liver become damaged. However, the liver failure is a life-threatening condition, it is difficult to detect without very concentrated analysis. This research work concentrates only on Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disorder (AFLD), which is the after effect of excessive alcoholic consumption.

3. Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disorder

The real time data collected from a famous hospital in Chennai city includes physically and clinically observed values about socioeconomic factors, physical factors, blood pressure, and blood results such as haematology, liver function test, lipid profile and plasma glucose analysis. An additional attention should be given to the factor estimation and preparation. Around 32 symptoms are collected from 18180 male patients to find the influence and depth of alcoholic fatty liver disorder in patients. In data mining, most of the techniques are depending upon a set of factors that describes the

behaviour of learning model. These attributes are the deciding factor for the acceptance level and complexity of the resulting model [14].

Fig.1: Age distribution of alcoholic fatty liver disorder

Table 1: distribution of Mean and Standard deviation of Age factor

Gender	Mean	SD
Male	50.23	4.634

The mean age of alcoholic fatty liver disorder is 50.23 and standard deviation is 4.634. The quantity of alcoholic consumption will increase after they settled in life and if their consumption started in earlier stage, their liver disorder will gradually developed after a period of time.

4. Methodology

Associative classification algorithms are indeed with the basic concept of this research, where frequently occurred pair of tuples used to figure an association rule [15]. Association mining is rule-based unsupervised machine learning. It searches for frequent items in a dataset. The interesting associations and correlations between itemset shows which items appear together in a transaction or relation. Classification is supervised machine learning which constructs an efficient model from training dataset. Associative classification is a supervised learning algorithm that integrates association rule mining and classification technique to generate more accurate results than any other traditionally used classification algorithms. In sequential covering algorithm, the instances presented in the rule are removed after the rule generation. Then, the learning is made with remaining tuples. In reverse of sequential covering algorithm [16], the tuples are identified from the end and moves towards the beginning to assemble conjunctions within the rule.

The rules are formed with the conjunctions of most frequent symptoms in the AFLD dataset. In Reverse Sequential Covering Algorithm (RSCA), weight of the rule is the key fact to identify the best fit rules. But in this research, the rules are created on the basis of support, confidence, lift, leverage and conviction.

$R \leftarrow \emptyset$
 Create R_1 to R_n
 $r \in R$ (where, $r = r_i, r_{i+1}, \dots, r_{i+n}$)
 \forall_r Compute support
 \forall_r Compute confidence
 If (support \geq minimum support) &&
 (confidence \geq minimum confidence)
 $\Rightarrow r_i \cup r_{i+1}$
 else prune r_{i+1}

The total instances of this study is 18180 and the minimum support is fixed as 0.6 to satisfy 60% probability in total dataset and confidence is fixed as 0.9 to verify rule's repetition in the analysis.

The physiological factors and clinical factors are separately used to generate the conjunctions of the symptoms. The physiological factors includes gender, age, itching, alcoholic consumption, smoking, obesity, fever, vomiting, abdomen pain, yellowish urinary discharge, low appetite, disturbance in abdomen, pale stools, chills, rigor, head ache and acting differently. The first and foremost 9 conjunctions of physiological observed symptoms are illustrated below.

1. Alcoholic Consumption \Rightarrow Vomiting
2. Alcoholic Consumption, Vomiting \Rightarrow Smoking
3. Alcoholic Consumption, Vomiting, Smoking \Rightarrow Abdomen pain
4. Alcoholic Consumption, Vomiting, Smoking, Abdomen pain \Rightarrow Rigor
5. Alcoholic Consumption, Vomiting, Smoking, Abdomen pain \Rightarrow Rigor
6. Alcoholic Consumption, Vomiting, Smoking, Abdomen pain, Rigor \Rightarrow Chills
7. Alcoholic Consumption, Vomiting, Smoking, Abdomen pain, Rigor, Chills \Rightarrow Yellowish urinary discharge
8. Alcoholic Consumption, Vomiting, Smoking, Abdomen pain, Rigor, Chills, Yellowish urinary discharge \Rightarrow low appetite
9. Alcoholic Consumption, Vomiting, Smoking, Abdomen pain, Rigor, Chills, Yellowish urinary discharge, low appetite \Rightarrow Disturbance in abdomen

$$\text{Support (Alcoholic Consumption)} = \frac{18180}{18180} = 1$$

$$\text{Support (Vomiting)} = \frac{17634}{18180} = 0.9699$$

Therefore,

$$\text{Support(Alcoholic Consumption} \Rightarrow \text{Vomiting)} = 0.9699$$

Confidence (Alcoholic Consumption \Rightarrow Vomiting)

$$= \frac{\text{Support (Alcoholic Consumption} \Rightarrow \text{Vomiting)}}{\text{Support (Alcoholic Consumption)}} = \frac{0.9699}{1} = 0.9699$$

Lift (Alcoholic Consumption \Rightarrow Vomiting)

$$= \frac{\text{Support (Alcoholic Consumption)} \cup \text{Support (Vomiting)}}{\text{Support(Alcoholic Consumption)} \times \text{Support(Vomiting)}} = 1 \cup 0.9699$$

Leverage (Alcoholic Consumption \Rightarrow Vomiting)

$$= P (\text{Alcoholic Consumption}) P (\text{Vomiting}) = 0.9699$$

Conviction (Alcoholic Consumption \Rightarrow Vomiting)

$$= \frac{1 - \text{Support (Vomiting)}}{1 - \text{Confidence (Alcoholic Consumption} \Rightarrow \text{Vomiting)}} \\ = \frac{1 - 0.9699}{1 - 0.9699} = 1$$

Since, alcoholic consumption is the major reason for the liver disease, the support of alcoholic consumption is 1. Vomiting is the common symptom in 17634 patients and so the support of vomiting is 0.9699. Therefore the confidence is also calculated as 0.9699. The lift is 2.0310, leverage is 0.9699 and conviction is 1. Lift is used to calculate the number of times more often Alcoholic Consumption and vomiting occur together than expected as these are independent symptoms. Leverage calculates the difference of Alcoholic Consumption and vomiting shows together in patients where, both are expected as dependent symptoms. Conviction evaluate the probability of Alcoholic Consumption appears without vomiting as dependent symptoms.

Similarly,

$$\text{Support (Alcoholic Consumption, Vomiting} \Rightarrow \text{Smoking)} = \frac{17024}{18180} = 0.9364$$

Confidence (Alcoholic Consumption, Vomiting \Rightarrow Smoking)

$$= \frac{\text{Support (Smoking)}}{\text{Support (Alcoholic Consumption, Vomiting)}} = \frac{0.9364}{0.9699} = 0.9655$$

Lift (Alcoholic Consumption, Vomiting \Rightarrow Smoking)

$$= \frac{\text{Support (Alcoholic Consumption, Vomiting)} \cup \text{Support (Smoking)}}{\text{Support (Alcoholic Consumption, Vomiting)} \times \text{Support (Smoking)}}$$

$$= \frac{0.9699 \cup 0.9394}{0.9699 \times 0.9394} = 2.0955$$

Leverage (Alcoholic Consumption, Vomiting => Smoking)

$$= P(\text{Alcoholic Consumption, Vomiting}) \times P(\text{Smoking}) = 1.8446$$

Conviction (Alcoholic Consumption => Vomiting)

$$= \frac{1 - \text{Support (Smoking)}}{1 - \text{Confidence (Alcoholic Consumption, Vomiting => Smoking)}}$$

$$= \frac{1 - 0.9364}{1 - 0.9655} = 1.8435$$

The 15 clinically collected symptoms used to create the rule are plasma glucose –F, plasma glucose –R, blood pressure (diastolic), blood pressure (systolic), triglycerides, DC polymorphs, DC eosiphils, DC basophils, DC mocytes, E.S.R., P.C.V., M.C.V., M.C.H., M.C.H.C. and platelet count. The foremost 9 conjunctions generated by support and confidence calculation are as follows.

1. Triglycerides =>DC Polymorphs
2. Triglycerides, DC Polymorphs => Plasma Glucose -R
3. Triglycerides, DC Polymorphs, Plasma Glucose - R => Plasma Glucose - F
4. Triglycerides, DC Polymorphs, Plasma Glucose - R, Plasma Glucose – F => Blood Pressure (Diastolic)
5. Triglycerides, DC Polymorphs, Plasma Glucose - R, Plasma Glucose - F=> Blood Pressure (Diastolic) => Blood Pressure (Systolic)
6. Triglycerides, DC Polymorphs, Plasma Glucose - R, Plasma Glucose - F=> Blood Pressure (Diastolic), Blood Pressure (Systolic) => DC Basophils
7. Triglycerides, DC Polymorphs, Plasma Glucose - R, Plasma Glucose - F=> Blood Pressure (Diastolic), Blood Pressure (Systolic), DC Basophils => E.S.R
8. Triglycerides, DC Polymorphs, Plasma Glucose - R, Plasma Glucose - F=> Blood Pressure (Diastolic), Blood Pressure (Systolic), DC Basophils, E.S.R => DC Eosiphils
9. Triglycerides, DC Polymorphs, Plasma Glucose - R, Plasma Glucose - F=> Blood Pressure (Diastolic), Blood Pressure (Systolic), DC Basophils, E.S.R, DC Eosiphils => M.C.V.

5. Significance of the Rule

Pearson correlation coefficient is used to find the significance between the confidence of of best conjunctions generated from physical and clinical factors.

Fig.2: The correlation between the confidence of Physical symptoms and Clinical symptoms

The X axis represents confidence of the rules generated from physical symptoms and Y represents confidence of the rules generated from clinical symptoms. The Pearson's $r = 0.9877$, so there a strong positive correlation between these two values. The 5th,6th and 7th rules from first dataset is having more confidence value than the same number of rules generated from clinical symptoms.

Table 2: Distribution of mean and r^2 in regression analysis

		Mean	r^2
Rule of Physical Symptoms	Leverage	1.3222	0.7453
	Conviction	1.4988	
Rule of Clinical Symptoms	Leverage	1.1516	0.8413
	Conviction	1.2534	

Fig.3: The regression of Leverage and Conviction in rules of Physical symptoms

The linear regression is used to analyse the relation between leverage and conviction where, Leverage represents X axis and Conviction represents Y axis. Figure 3 represents the regression between leverage and conviction values of the conjunctions generated from the physical symptoms. The mean of leverage is 1.32 and conviction is 1.5. The r^2 is 75% and so there is a chance for majority of values to fit the regression model.

$$\text{Regression line equation of Physical Symptoms} = 0.35058446245045 + 0.86839388197469x$$

Fig.4: The regression of Leverage and Conviction in rules of Clinical symptoms

Figure 4 represents the regression between leverage and conviction of the conjunctions from the clinically observed values. The mean of leverage is 1.15 and conviction is 1.25. The r^2 of this regression is 84% and so there is a chance for maximum values to fit the regression model. This regression is having high rate of fitting than physical values.

$$\text{Regression line equation Clinical Symptoms} = 0.35273096034223 + 0.78207004128629x$$

6. Conclusion

The support and confidence is applied with reverse sequential covering algorithm to generate best fit rules from physically and clinically observed symptoms of alcoholic fatty liver disordered patients. Alcoholic fatty liver disorder is the result of continues or excessive alcoholic consumptions. Initially, 17 physical symptoms of 18180 patients are used to generate the rules and first 9 conjunctions are explained here. Then, 15 clinical symptoms are used to predict the disease and first 9 conjunctions are also illustrated in this work. The confidence correlation between both set of conjunctions are analysed and found a positive correlation. So conjunction of both set of rules can be used for better prediction of disease before making further clinical analysis for alcoholic fatty liver disorder. The linear regression of leverage and conviction are made separately for both sets and found positive correlation in all cases and therefore, maximum values between leverage and conviction were fit the regression model. In further studies, the accuracy of this rule can be compared with other machine learning algorithms.

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